

Handling of Form, Style Markers and Authorial Identity: Two Case Studies around the Work of Carlos Seixas

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As I suggested elsewhere, authorship attribution is one of the issues related to the keyboard works of Carlos Seixas (1704-42) that has been generally mistreated.¹ The problem arises from two different, though related circumstances. On the one hand, a critical appraisal of the body of sources containing Seixas's keyboard works has never been attempted until quite recently and only partially to the present. On the other hand, the editions and writings of Santiago Kastner (and others following him) established a long-lasting and somehow inhibiting authority in the approach to the composer's output. This resulted in the unquestioning acceptance of a number of seemingly arbitrary attributions and rejections of pieces presented in the manuscript sources either anonymously or ambiguously as to their authorship.

Although heavily influenced by Kastner's judgements, Klaus Heimes discusses in his unpublished 1967 doctoral dissertation the subjects of form and style in the keyboard sonatas of Carlos Seixas in the light of Iberian and European contexts, suggesting several useful criteria in the establishing of the composer's canon.² A few, more recent studies — especially the 1992 article by Manuel Pedro Ferreira on the *Sinfonia in B flat major*³ — extended the discussion of authorship attribution on the basis of form and style analysis to Seixas's orchestral works. And a preliminary

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¹ João Pedro d'Alvarenga, 'Some Preliminaries in Approaching Carlos Seixas' Keyboard Sonatas', *Ad Parnassum: A Journal of Eighteenth- and Nineteenth-Century Instrumental Music* vii/13 (2009), 95-128 at 101-2.

² Klaus Ferdinand Heimes, 'Carlos Seixas's Keyboard Sonatas' (Ph.D. diss., Pretoria, University of South Africa, 1967).

³ Manuel Pedro Ferreira, 'A Sinfonia em Sib maior de Carlos Seixas (?): notas sobre o estilo, a data e o autor', *Revista Portuguesa de Musicologia* 2 (1992), 147-60.

catalogue of the sonatas (along with the study of their four main manuscript sources held by the National Library of Portugal) was at last published in 2009.⁴

In this paper, I will propose the attribution to Seixas of an anonymous work previously rejected by Kastner and others — the keyboard Concerto in G minor — summarizing the reasoning of my recent article on this piece,⁵ and the deattribution of an equally anonymous Sonata in A major, numbered App. 19-2 in the preliminary catalogue of the sonatas.

The Harpsichord Concerto in G minor is a much longer and complex piece than Seixas's well-known and undisputed Harpsichord Concerto in A major.⁶ Both pieces are in three movements. Unlike the latter, the G minor Concerto has a clearly post-Baroque idiom and there is a penchant for *galant* style, for most of its material is based on a succession of short and differentiated motifs more melodically conceived, often with immediate repeats or in sequential arrangement, with relatively less figuration but more decoration. On the basis of stylistic and constructional criteria I have dated the A major Concerto to no later than the middle of the 1730s and the G minor Concerto to between around 1740 and the date of Seixas's death in 1742.⁷

For the purpose of discussing the attribution of the G minor Concerto to Carlos Seixas, we just need to consider its last movement which, although notated in 3/8 time, is a giga, marked *Allegro assai*.⁸ Despite the tutti-solo alternation, the movement essentially constitutes an extended two-reprise form in the familiar polar-type tonal scheme i-v :||: v (-III/v)-i (see TABLE 1). Large-scale parallelisms strengthen its binary structure: materials in the five-minor key area (in bars 70-123¹) in the first part are correspondingly transposed and adapted to the tonic in the second part (as bars 198-251¹). After the insertion of a previously-heard ascending chromatic motif in bars 251²-

⁴ Alvarenga, 'Some Preliminaries', Appendix 1, 110-23, and Appendix 2, 124-28.

⁵ João Pedro d'Alvarenga, 'Carlos Seixas's Harpsichord Concerto in G Minor: An Essay in Style Analysis and Authorship Attribution', *Ad Parnassum: A Journal of Eighteenth- and Nineteenth-Century Instrumental Music* x/19 (2012), forthcoming.

⁶ Modern editions of the A major Concerto: *Carlos Seixas: Concerto em Lá maior para cravo e orquestra de arcos*, ed. Pierre Salzmann, Portugaliae Musica 15 (Lisbon, Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian, 1969); *Carlos Seixas: Concerto para cravo e cordas*, ed. Ivo Cruz (Lisbon, Conservatório Nacional, 1971); *Carlos Seixas: Concerto para cravo em Lá maior*, ed. João Pedro d'Alvarenga (non-commercial edition, Lisbon, 1993). Modern editions of the G minor Concerto: *Anonymus Coimbra MM 59 (18. Jahrhunderts) Konzert g-moll für Cembalo und Streicher*, ed. Gerhard Doderer (Heidelberg, Willy Müller Süddeutscher Musikverlag, 1979); *Carlos Seixas: Concerto para cravo em sol menor*, ed. João Pedro d'Alvarenga (non-commercial edition, Lisbon, 2003).

⁷ See Alvarenga, 'Carlos Seixas's Harpsichord Concerto in G Minor', forthcoming.

⁸ A full discussion of both the A major and G minor harpsichord concertos can be found in the article referred to in note 5.

255¹ (x), the last tutti in the first part (bars 123²-139) is also entirely restated, obviously properly transposed, for the closing of the last tutti in the second part (as bars 255²-271).

As usual in many of Seixas's bipartite sonatas, material and tonality converge around the structural points of modulation on each side of the double bar. An often-quoted example of this characteristic constructional device is the first movement of Sonata no. 6-6 in D minor (see EXAMPLE 1).

EXAMPLE 1. Seixas, Sonata no. 6-6 in D minor, first movement, bars 8-12 and 33-36: The interaction between material and tonality around the structural points of modulation

In the G minor Concerto, the distinct material in bars 58-69, just before the strong cadence that establishes the secondary key, is also paralleled in bars 186-197, preceding the re-establishment of the tonic key area (see again TABLE 1 and EXAMPLE 2). This binary structure is further balanced also at the beginning, as the head-motif (M) — a descending arpeggio of the I chord with anacrusis — appears at the opening of the first tutti and the consequent solo in the first part, and at the beginning of the first solo in the second part, each time further expanded from two to three and four octaves respectively, thus making use of the entire compass of the average harpsichords then available.⁹

⁹ Which in Portuguese instruments was *C-d'''* for the long period between about 1725 and 1790. Instruments with the compass *C-e'''* were also in use apparently between 1740 and 1780 (although the oldest extant harpsichord with such a compass, made in Lisbon by Joaquim José Antunes, is dated 1758); see Gerhard Doderer and John Henry Van der Meer, *Portuguese String Keyboard Instruments of the 18th Century: Clavichords, Harpsichords, Fortepianos and Spinets* (Lisbon, Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian, 2005), 325-28.

TABLE 1. Timeline of Harpsichord Concerto in G minor, third movement.

tutti	S		tutti	S	tutti S tutti
: 1 - 21	22-	58-	70-		- 139 :
i → ^v /i	i	→	v		close
M	M		x - x		

S	-tutti-S-tutti-S-tutti S	tutti	S-tutti-S	tutti S tutti
: 140-	186-	198-		[251 ² -255 ¹] - 271 :
v	→ ^{III} /v →	i		close
M		x - x	x	

 parallel post-modulation material

The style markers of Carlos Seixas were long-ago discussed in Klaus Heimes's dissertation, and summarized in two recent articles by the present author.¹⁰ Style markers are set formulas recurring in the bulk of the pieces unequivocally attributed to the composer. Of course no one is exclusive to Seixas's music and some are even part of the 'International' late-Baroque and post-Baroque idioms. But if cumulatively considered in the context of other significant constructional criteria, they become markers of authorial identity. Actually, most of these markers are present in the G minor Concerto. Let us just look at: (a) the use of conclusions in open octaves; (b) the progression from subdominant minor over dominant to the tonic repeated on a characteristic $\flat\hat{6}-\hat{5}-\flat\hat{6}-\hat{5}$ bass line; and (c) the use of melodic patterns with fragmentation of the strong beat of the bar with resulting syncopations.

Conclusions in open octaves can be seen throughout Seixas's instrumental music, regardless of the character of the individual pieces. This is probably his most conspicuous gesture and need no further examples here. Conclusions in open octaves are present in the G minor Concerto in the closing of its first and second movements and on both parts of its last movement.

¹⁰ Heimes, 'Carlos Seixas's Keyboard Sonatas', 268-83; João Pedro d'Alvarenga, Carlos Seixas: um esboço biográfico e uma leitura sintética da sua obra', *Águas Furtadas: Revista de Literatura, Música e Artes Visuais*, 10 (2006), 172, and id., 'Some Preliminaries', 102-4.

57 Pre-modulation material →

64 Point of modulation to v^{vns}

71 Post-modulation material →
va omitted
b

185 Pre-modulation material →

192 Point of modulation to i^{vns}

199 Post-modulation material →
va omitted
b

EXAMPLE 2. Harpsichord Concerto in G minor, third movement, bars 57-78 and 185-206

The progression from subdominant minor over dominant to the tonic repeated on a $b\hat{6}-\hat{5}-b\hat{6}-\hat{5}$ bass line can be seen in the G minor Concerto for example, in the third movement in the second phrase of the first tutti, bars 11-21, and in the corresponding place of the first solo section, bars 37-42 (see EXAMPLE 3). This peculiar progression is also used by Domenico Scarlatti, Antonio Soler and occasionally by some other

Portuguese composers.¹¹ But again Seixas employed it with such consistency in movements of so different nature that it became a formula and a major characteristic of his style. For example, Sonata no. 20-9 in A minor deploys the formula in a more contrapuntal context (see EXAMPLE 4); Minuet no. 19-13 in A major for example, presents it in a lighter texture, comparable to that of Concerto in G minor (see EXAMPLE 5).

EXAMPLE 3. Harpsichord Concerto in G minor, third movement, bars 36-42

EXAMPLE 4. Seixas, Sonata no. 20-9 in A minor, bars 54-58

EXAMPLE 5. Seixas, Minuet no. 19-13 in A major, bars 16-21

¹¹ This is what Dean Sutcliffe discusses as ‘the Phrygian progression’; see W. Dean Sutcliffe, *The Keyboard Sonatas of Domenico Scarlatti and Eighteenth-Century Musical Style* (Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2003), 116-18; see also Heimes, ‘Carlos Seixas’s Keyboard Sonatas’, 242 and 273-74. Note that conclusions in open octaves and the alternating $\flat\hat{6}-\hat{5}$ bass are also found in Scarlatti’s K. 97 (whose sole source is the c.1746 Boivin-Le Clerc printing, *Pieces pour le clavecin Composées par Domenico Scarlatti. Troisième volume*), which it has been suggested might be by Seixas. However, the compass required in K. 97 reaches e''' (in bar 109). This would be rather odd for Seixas, whose sonatas never go beyond d''' .

The fragmentation of the strong beat of the bar with resulting syncopations, although also found in Scarlatti and other Iberian composers,¹² is another highly characteristic formula of Seixas's style, which he uses in a variety of rhythmic and melodic arrangements, within movements of disparate character. Clear parallels with the motifs of bars 97-109 (and correspondingly, of bars 225-237) in the third movement of Concerto in G minor (see EXAMPLE 6) can be seen for example, in Sonata no. 16-7 in G minor (see EXAMPLE 7) and Sonata no. 2-8 in C minor (see EXAMPLE 8).

EXAMPLE 6. Harpsichord Concerto in G minor, third movement, bars 97-109

EXAMPLE 7. Seixas, Sonata no. 16-7 in G minor, bars 9-14

¹² See Klaus Ferdinand Heimes, 'Antonio Soler's Keyboard Sonatas' (M.Mus. diss., Pretoria, University of South Africa, 1965), 216, and id., 'Carlos Seixas's Keyboard Sonatas', 276-78.

EXAMPLE 8. Seixas, Sonata no. 2-8 in C minor, bars 39-45

An apparently special feature of Seixas's binary-ritornello forms, as seen in the third movements of both the A major and G minor Concertos — and unlike what happens for example, in the third movements of Francesco Durante's B flat major Harpsichord Concerto or Giovanni Benedetto Platti's G major and C minor Harpsichord Concertos¹³ — is to include the second tutti in the first part of the movement and to proceed with a solo section right after the double bar instead of beginning the second part with a tutti section parallel to the first tutti in the movement. This allows for textural alternation across the double bar and for the entire secondary-key material in the first part to be transposed to the tonic key in the second part, thus achieving a perfectly balanced structure, more congruent with post-baroque binary-form principles.¹⁴ Finally, the particular type of convergence of material and tonality around the structural points of modulation on each side of the double bar in two-reprise form, which involves the parallelism not only of post-modulation material but also of the material immediately preceding it, as seen in the third movement of the G minor Concerto, is definitely a hallmark of Seixas.¹⁵

Unlike the G minor Concerto, Sonata App. 19-2 in A major has a markedly different identity and a near-Classical flavour. It appears unattributed in the second part of manuscript Lisbon, Biblioteca Nacional, MM 338, just before Domenico Scarlatti's F minor Sonata K. 50 (also anonymous in this source). The second part of MM 338 originated together with the third part of manuscript Lisbon, Biblioteca Nacional, MM 337, with which it shares the main paper-types, the copyist and the kind of repertory.

¹³ Edited by Francesco Degrada (Milano, Ricordi, 1968) and Fausto Torrefranca (Milano, Ricordi, 1949, and 1953) respectively.

¹⁴ For Durante's and Platti's examples, see Daniel E. Freeman, 'The Earliest Italian Keyboard Concertos', *The Journal of Musicology* iv/2 (1985-86), 130-31.

¹⁵ See Heimes, 'Carlos Seixas's Keyboard Sonatas', 84 ff. especially at 88-89, 97, and 112-17; Alvarenga, 'Carlos Seixas: um esboço biográfico', 174-75, and id., 'Some Preliminaries', 104.

Both manuscript pieces, probably constituting an originally single volume, are positively dated to 1774-75.¹⁶ Heimes discussed at full the authorship of Sonata App. 19-2 in A major, which he considered ‘rather unusual’ when compared to ‘the descriptions, diagrams, and examples’ he gives of other sonatas by Seixas. His many doubts on its authorship are well expressed, but he was advised by Kastner ‘to keep an open mind on the question of the authenticity’ of this piece. It was so accepted and has since remained among the works conjecturally attributed to Seixas.¹⁷ However, none of the style markers of Seixas appear on this sonata.

I will not repeat Heimes’s line of argument and description of its characteristics, but a look at TABLE 2 makes apparent that Sonata App. 19-2 in A major has an overall ternary thematic disposition over the simple polar-type tonal scheme I-V :||: V-I.¹⁸ The initial material emancipates as a proper first theme, not only because of its periodic structure, but specifically because of its restatement early in the second part of the movement after the double bar simultaneously with the return modulation, after a brief development of a separate idea derived from the second theme. Since in the second part the first theme is not immediately repeated as in the opening, and the second and third themes are discarded, being replaced by a different yet contrasting theme, the reprise is of a modified or varied type (see EXAMPLE 9).

TABLE 2. Timeline of Sonata App. 19-2 in A major

: 1	-9	10	-18	19	-27 ¹	- ²	-35 :
I	→ ^D /I	V					
t1+t1 ²		t2	t3		K1=t4		

: 36	-41	42	-46	47	-53	-55 ¹	- ²	-63 ¹	- ²	-70/	-74 :
(V)	→	I									
X(>t2)		t1 ²	t5	∩	t4		K2(>X)			coda	

¹⁶ For a description and dating of the manuscripts, see Alvarenga, ‘Some Preliminaries’, 125-26. Both MM 337 and MM 338 are now digitized at <<http://purl.pt/14380>> and <<http://purl.pt/16631>> respectively.

¹⁷ Heimes, ‘Carlos Seixas’s Keyboard Sonatas’, 139-45. Sonata App. 19-2 in A major had been published as ‘Sonata 60’ in *Carlos Seixas: 80 Sonatas para instrumentos de tecla*, ed. Macario Santiago Kastner, Portugaliae Musica 10 (Lisbon, Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian, 1965) and was subsequently published as ‘Sonata XXVII’ in *Carlos Seixas: Ausgewählte Sonaten XVI-XXX*, ed. Gerhard Doderer, Organa Hispanica VIII (Heidelberg, Willy Müller, Süddeutscher Musikverlag, 1982).

¹⁸ On the roots and early development of ternary structures in eighteenth-century instrumental music, see Klaus Ferdinand Heimes, ‘The Ternary Sonata Principle before 1742’, *Acta Musicologica* 45/2 (1973), 222-48.

Allegro

6

12

36

41

47

EXAMPLE 9. Sonata App. 19-2 in A major, bars 1-16 and 36-53

The point is that such sort of interaction between material and tonality has no parallel in the music of Seixas and indeed in any known piece by a Portuguese composer datable to the first half of the eighteenth century. Among Seixas's

authenticated sonatas, there is however a couple of examples of a formal type quite common in the works of such ‘transitional’, mid-century composers as Johann Joachim Quantz, Platti, Carl Philipp Emanuel and Johann Christian Bach, where the initial material is restated right after the double bar in the dominant key and again fully or partially restated after the return modulation in the tonic, the whole structure being further balanced by parallel closings:¹⁹ those of Sonata no. 20-3 in A minor for organ²⁰ and Sonata no. 9-1 in E major.²¹ Occurrences of this or similar formal types became common in Portuguese keyboard sonatas of the 1760s and 1770s. Some of the earliest datable examples are the first movements of Francisco Xavier Baptista’s ‘Sonata II’, ‘Sonata V’ and ‘Sonata XI’, from his *Dodeci Sonate*, printed in Lisbon sometime between 1765 and 1777.²²

Besides becoming frequent in more or less extensive rounded-binary minuets as for instance, Manuel Elias’s Minuet in D major,²³ the overall type of structuring of Sonata App. 19-2 in A major also occurs in two of Baptista’s *Dodeci Sonate*, namely the first movements of ‘Sonata IX’ and ‘Sonata X’.²⁴ In minuets (including some second movements in Baptista’s printing), however, and in a number of sonatas, like Pedro António Avondano’s Sonata in C major,²⁵ the relatively late placement of the tonic incipit after the double bar leaves little or no room for another restatement area to succeed it. But in Baptista’s first movements, just referred to, handling of form is similar to Sonata App. 19-2: ternary thematic organisation runs over a simple polar-type tonal plan; materials in complementary key areas are well contrasted; restatement of the

¹⁹ There are examples of this type of thematic organisation dating back to the 1710s; see Heimes, ‘The Ternary Sonata Principle’, 234 ff.

²⁰ ‘Fuga 15’ in *Cravistas portuguesas II*, ed. M. S. Kastner (Mainz, Schott, 1950); ‘Sonata 76’ in *Carlos Seixas: 80 Sonatas*, ed. Kastner; and ‘Sonata XXIX’ in *Carlos Seixas: Ausgewählte Sonaten*, ed. Doderer.

²¹ ‘Sonata X’ in *Carlos Seixas: 25 Sonatas para instrumentos de tecla*, ed. Macario Santiago Kastner and João Valeriano, *Portugaliae Musica* 34 (Lisbon, Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian, 1980). Sonata no. 9-1 is a *unicum* in manuscript P-Ln CIC 110, where Seixas’s authorship is stated just on the front-cover and supposedly intended for the whole volume. However, some of its contents can be attributed to different composers; see Alvarenga, ‘Some Preliminaries’, 101. Manuscript P-Ln CIC 110 is digitized at <<http://purl.pt/16534>>.

²² Modern edition in *Francisco Xavier Baptista (+ 1797): 12 Sonatas para cravo (Lisboa, ca. 1770)*, ed. Gerhard Doderer, *Portugaliae Musica* 36 (Lisbon, Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian, 1981). On the dating of the original printing, see Maria João Durães Albuquerque, *A edição musical em Portugal (1750-1834)*, *Estudos Musicológicos* 29 (Lisbon, Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian, IN-CM, 2006), 119-24, 200.

²³ *Minuete de Fr. Manuel Elias*, Lisbon, Biblioteca Nacional, MM 86//15; modern edition in *Portugiesische Sonaten, Toccaten und Menuette des 18. Jahrhunderts*, ed. Gerhard Doderer, *Organa Hispanica II* (Heidelberg, Willy Müller, Süddeutscher Musikverlag, 1972), 38-40. Curiously, Elias uses Seixas’s ‘Phrygian progression’ for the return modulation.

²⁴ ‘Sonata IX’ appears in a longer, possibly earlier version and coupled with a different minuet in the first part of manuscript MM 338, dated to 1765. For the dating, see Alvarenga, ‘Some Preliminaries’, 125-26.

²⁵ No. 2 in the late-eighteenth-century manuscript F-Pn Vm⁷ 4874; unpublished.

first theme in the tonic arrives early in the second part of the movement after a brief development or a separate idea; the reprise is varied either by pruning or amplification and parallel closings are restricted to the very last bars. There are significant differences, as shown in the substitution of an alternative second theme in the second part in Sonata App. 19-2, but the three sonatas have the same interaction of material and tonality and the same clearly defined thematic components. Rhythmical periodisation, motif repetition and delicate melodic chromaticism mark these works as a whole.

In short, the characteristics of Sonata App. 19-2 suit well the stylistic and constructional trends in Portuguese keyboard music of the 1760s and 1770s. Even with an 'open mind' as to the question of its authorship, we can but assign this work to the period immediately preceding the copying of the manuscript containing it. Whoever its composer was, he surely was more gifted and architecturally resourceful than the average. It is however clear that Seixas, who died in 1742, could not have been that composer.